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MAPPING THE LANDSCAPE OF LIFE IN THE POETRY OF JAYANTA MAHAPATRA

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Jayanta Mahapatra, the Sahitya Akademi award winner for *Relationship* in 1981 is a very reflective and serious poet who, by virtue of his poetic art, turned his local poetry into the global poetry. On 27 August, 2023, Death took him away from this mundane world. The poet is dead, not his poetry. Life has its dwelling in words. He attempts to decipher the mysterious script of life in his poetry. This paper explores the various dimensions of Mahapatra's poetry and reveals his contribution to the field of Indian Poetry in English through excerpts from almost all his poetry collections.

"I can't remember hearing anyone saying he will mourn for me when I am gone." (*Life Signs* 39)

This is what Jayanta Mahapatra (22 October 1928 - 27 August, 2023) wrote in his poem "Again, One Day, Walking by the River," published in *Life Signs* in 1983. What he writes here cannot be applied to Jayanta Mahapatra himself as every lover of poetry mourns for him. One can meet him in words of his poems. Mahapatra himself believes that life has its dwelling in words:

In words
our lives
dwell. (*Dispossessed Nest* 32)

Besides editing the reputed journal *Chandrabhaga*, Mahapatra penned poetry collections, namely, *Close the Sky, Ten By Ten* (1971), *Svayamvara and Other Poems* (1971), *A Father's Return* (1976), *A Rain of Rites* (1976), *Waiting* (1979), *Relationship* (1980), *The False Start* (1980), *Life Signs* (1983), *Dispossessed Nests* (1986), *Burden of Waves and Fruits* (1988), *Temple* (1989), *A Whiteness of Bone* (1992), *Shadow Space* (1997), *Bare Face* (2000), *Random Descent* (2005), *The Lie of Dawns* (2009), *Land* (2013), *Hesitant Light* (2016), and *Noon: New and Selected Poems* (2023). Jayanta Mahapatra's poetry collection *Relationship* makes him the first Indian poet who got the Sahitya Akademi award for English poetry. He also got the Padma Shri in 2009 but returned it in 2015 because of "rising intolerance" in India. The pages of his poetry collections bubble with the ingredients like myth, history, Indian sensibility, contemporary socio-political reality, human relationship, Orissian landscape, self and the other. Myths, symbols and metaphors colour the pages of his poetry collections.

Going through his poems makes the reader see in Mahapatra a mental gymnast. U. R. Ananthamurthy calls him "an intensely subjective poet, and a fiercely honest person," but finds in him "a difficult poet to read" (ix) because of his use of language. He frankly assesses his poetry stating: "He does not always speak out to us, we overhear him" (ix). For Alan Kennedy, "Jayanta Mahapatra is hard to read" (75). Bruce King takes his poetry to be "unusual" (14) and finds the nearest 'English' model in Dylan Thomas. R. C. Shukla calls Mahapatra "a silken poet with very thin threads" and finds him "too gentle to thunder" (*Discovery* 115).

If some critics find him a difficult poet, there are many other critics like C. B. Cox, John Oliver Perry, Niranjana Mohanty, P. Laxminarayana Bhat, Madhusudan Prasad, Rabindra K. Swain and Vilas Sarang who appreciate him for creating a new idiom in Indian poetry in English. While assessing Mahapatra's poetry, Vilas Sarang writes: "Mahapatra's poetry is a phenomenon of special significance, for it seems to point toward the direction that Indian English poetry will take most fruitfully. Extremely local, it has, at the same time, an international quality" (31). "Mahapatra," writes Niranjana Mohanty, "remains the best of all the contemporary Indian poets in English" (70). For Madhusudan Prasad, "Mahapatra's poetry both in quality as well as quantity is impressive and refreshing" (vi).

Mahapatra's poetry reflects his tragic consciousness. Pain remains inseparable from poetry. In an interview, he shares with Norman Simms that "Life is painful, the process of writing a poem is painful, and then poetry is going into and finding the centre of yourself, and I suppose you can't do this if you don't give up your own self" (311). A poet is equipped more with empathy than with sympathy. He has to give up his own self in order to enter other's self. He is "a man who talks of pain/ as though it belonged to him alone" (*Whiteness* 36). He voices his feelings in words though he has some doubts. But, with the passage of time, he becomes confident enough to think that "When all else has failed,/ the poem's words are perhaps justified" (*Life Signs* 34). Poetry for him becomes "an attempt to remove the burden of time" (*Door* 5) as he finds himself "caught up in a net of time" (*Door* 219). A poem is a waterless river. The poet feels the flow of this river at the subconscious level from where it finds its flowing path on the white sheet of a paper in order to take the form of a poem.

Today

I stand on the bank of the poem
 even though each word has a price,
 even though this poetry appears as a river,
 a river without water
 we have to swim across,
 and even if its words

do not welcome us to its secret country
where we live without knowing. (*Shadow Space* 61)

Jayanta Mahapatra does not write poems, poetry makes him write poems. He frankly admits that he writes when he feels bad. His heart is burdened. Poetry unburdens him by giving him an outlet to his heart. He states:

Poetry makes me write poems with a bad heart. I don't know what that exactly means, but it is the heart that makes one turn secretly into someone – a leader or loser – pushing one to choose values, attitudes, and to do the not-so-obvious; this heart, as it keeps on trying to hide the wounded walls of its house, and at the same time asking itself for a meaning to our lives. (*Door* 171)

Alan Kennedy seems to be right when he says: "Mahapatra will write 'bad' poetry, both deliberately and because of an inability, an inability to do anything else" (76). His heart feels bad, helpless, hopeless and frustrated when he sees the contemporary scenario, dotted with all the evils. This contemporary scene creates despair and isolation in his heart to the extent that he develops a tragic consciousness. He cries in words, myths and symbols, but his crying remains confined to the words of the poem without setting the wrong things right. Then he feels that he is "a poet who barks like a dog" (*Whiteness* 31). He begins to realize: "The poetry I write bruises the page" (*Bare Face* 39). For him, poetry becomes "a coquette that keeps telling her little secrets" (*Bare Face* 39). He continues to pen poem after poem with the hope of redemption.

Jayanta Mahapatra is an exceptional poet who never sees his fractured identity (Christian and Hindu) as hurdle. His Oriya feelings never obstruct him when he writes in English. He peeps into his self and realizes: "I am never anything but myself" (*Random Descent* 68). While searching for his identity, he associates himself with the landscape.

A man does not mean anything.
But the place.
Sitting on the riverbank throwing pebbles
into the muddy current,
a man becomes the place. (*Rites* 42)

He searches for his identity not only in Cuttack, which is the land of his birth, but in temples, rivers, landscapes, stones etc. He knows that somewhere he is also a part of the crowd where he stands. "Strange is the place to which you never belong./ But somewhere among the crowd you are there. (*Dispossessed Nests* 44). In his 'Acceptance Speech on Receiving the Sahitya Akademi Award for *Relationship*, 1981', he states:

To Orissa, to this land in which my roots lie and lies my past, and in which lies my beginning and my end, where the wind over the great

grief of the River Daya and where the waves of the Bay of Bengal fail to reach out today to the twilight soul of Konark, I acknowledge my debt and my relationship. (*Door* 81)

In *Relationship*, he seems to connect himself with the roots which link him to the myths, legends and history of Orissa in particular and of India in general. He searches for the timeless dimension of the Sun Temple and associates himself with the carved figures. These carved figures seem to be guiding him with a vision—the vision which he has got after removing the materialistic veil. His quest is not simply his own individual quest, but of multitudes as no one can feel at ease if he does not associate himself with his roots that lie in his traditions, culture, myth and the past. He dedicates himself at the altar of his origins because he knows: "I know I can never come alive/ if I refuse to consecrate at the altar of my origins" (*Relationship* 18). His relationship with the stone develops a sense of belongingness which makes him see, feel, grip and hear even the figures in stone. This process of relatedness enlivens him to the vision for future. He himself admits when he says: "and yet my existence lies in the stones/ which carry my footsteps from one day into another/ down to the infinite distances." (*Relationship* 11) Stone has become "the theme" (*Waiting* 8) for his songs. From the stone, he learns silence which helps him in creating "an air of mystery" that makes him "reach into the unknown" (*Door* 23) and sense the things unfelt before.

Rabindra K. Swain traces Mahapatra's visionary world and finds it "characterized by pain and suffering, memory and loss, hope and the possibilities of redemption." (7) What makes his poetry striking as well as mysterious is the presentation of life and its predicament. Life is itself mysterious because of its uncertainty. P. Laxminarayan Bhatt writes in this connection:

Mahapatra portrays the inherent uncertainty of human life and its predicament. This awareness makes Mahapatra restless, ambiguous and also highly creative. Therefore, the nature of his poetic probe into the essence of human life becomes equally complex and challenging which demands a serious approach to the understanding of his poetry. (199-200)

The poet in Mahapatra begins his journey of life in order to decipher the mysterious script of life. While standing on the shore, he starts musing about life and the related questions. The shore makes him think about the question of his own relevance. "The shore keeps me thinking/ why I have come into the world" (*Random Descent* 75). He associates himself with the whole mankind and thinks that his question is not his question alone but of all the human beings. Hence, he moves ahead to find the answer of his question. He states: "If I seek an answer to our life/ it's because I see myself everywhere,/ all the time" (*Random Descent* 75).

Even in the evening of his life, Mahapatra is in love of life so profoundly that he begins to embrace it in spite of various questions that arise in his heart. As Tennyson muses over crossing in "Crossing the Bar," Mahapatra also thinks of crossing from this world to the other world. While living in ignorance, a man considers night as morning and morning as night. When he is awakened to his self, he realizes the significance of the morning. Life is born out of death. The morning is the farewell from this world, but no one wishes for such farewell. Attachment to this world does not allow anyone to think of the bars that one has to cross in order to reach the other world. His own heart "beats into barriers of night" (*Hesitant Light* 13). The poet now knows this truth but, even then, his questioning nature makes him skeptic enough to ask:

And now should I tie my life
that is being born out of death
for one night, realizing well
that the morning
already means farewell the living never ask? (*Hesitant Light* 13)

The poet in Mahapatra feels that his own world is so small that he finds himself always visible before his own self. "My own world/ is so small. I'm always in front of myself" (*Hesitant Light* 17). He thinks that he is not in a position to comment anything about life. He makes his portrait with words and concludes: "I have nothing to declare" (*Hesitant Light* 37) because "It's no use declaring anything/ about the man perhaps I did not know at all" (*Hesitant Light* 38). He feels that he is lost in the web of the body. He does not know how to come out of the worldly allurements. He admits: "Sometimes I lose my way/ beginning with the body/ in the nothingness of a dream" (*Svayamvara* 6). Life is a puzzle that a man continues to solve throughout his life. He finds himself "torn between/ the desire to know, and fear of knowing" without realizing that he will have "to live in the future/ in order to face the sleepless nights of the present" (*Hesitant Light* 38). It is surprising that man does not see his own real self and always longs for the masks. "The urge to wear new masks/ has never ended/ it grows, unnoticed" (*Hesitant Light* 38). He continues to live in future while thinking of the past resulting in crushing the flowers of the present. He never lives in the things which he has made for himself. The poet states: "But what makes sense unless one lives in things/ made by ourselves" (*Burden* 15). His endeavor is to know others without knowing his own self. He remains in the world without knowing the real purpose of his life. The poet very frankly admits when he says:

Still I do not know what I want
I like to be here a long time
but that wouldn't help me to make sense.
I'm not sure I know myself yet. (*Burden* 57)

The poet is a human being and believes in human relationship. As he is a human being, he knows that "To be human/ is to see in a dream perhaps/ the one who can never be seen (*Dispossessed Nests* 20). He measures the dimensions of life, but fails because of its constant changes resulting in loneliness and solitude. A man wants to live of his own accord, but it never happens as it creates emptiness in him. It depends on man how he takes life whether positively or negatively. His shadow responds to him as he takes life to be. If he learns from the past and moves ahead, it is a good sign. Past, he thinks, is "the foundation over which the present rests" and, so, life seems to be moving "about the axis of the past" (*Waiting* 13). But he lives in the past and digs it deep in order to search for his shadow. He does not find it; rather he himself becomes a shadow. Very poignantly and philosophically, the poet presents the picture of life and its shadow thus:

And if you feel you are alone
because of your misunderstanding with life,
your shadow will go on treating you
as though you are already condemned.
Life, you would think then,
is a stupid wind that has lost its wings.
And if you open your past enough
to see into your own shadow,
you all but become the shadow itself. (*Hesitant Light* 88)

The poet takes the reader into the memory lane where he seems to be talking about his relatives, Orissan landscapes, art, sculptures, rain, stones, love, life, loss, grief, death, time, loneliness, despair and silence. Now he feels that "his memory is so full" that he likes "to lose more of it" (*Hesitant Light* 52). For him, stones have "turned to gods through prayers" (*Random Descent* 47) while time has become "just a pilgrimage/ that the mind makes between our uncertainties" (*Life Sign* 32). "Loneliness," for him, "is when an act, a word/ hangs undecided and unborn/ in the eyes of longing" (*Close the Sky* 1). It is surprising that "The laughter in the world/ is always on the lookout for grief" (*Shadow Space* 42) while the grief leads man nowhere. "Grief, and more grief, taking us nowhere" (*Hesitant Light* 28). Grief embraces man and makes him see death everywhere. The poet doubts whether grief will allow him to do what he wishes. "Can grief let me do what I wish,/ littering every corner of this dark/ with awakenings of death" (*False Start* 19)? Death becomes "a handcart" which one pushes "through a dayful of moonlight" (*False Start* 78). Finally, he sees silence as his companion even in rain, sleep and stone. Silence remains "the only evidence/ left behind, strange solace/ for mankind" (*Dispossessed Nests* 31). His whole life is "made up of silences" while discourses consume the time "trying to keep up with the past" (*Random Descent* 77).

Life's domain remains unexplored. The more a man explores it, the more unexplored he finds it. Hence, it is better if life is enjoyed with pleasure. It becomes possible when one does what one loves. "To live one must do those things one loves, / but always in secret" (*Whiteness* 24). The need is to see life in all its colours. There may be good in evil and evil in good. It depends on perception what one takes it to be. Where there is darkness, there may be light, and where there is light, there may be darkness. Mahapatra seems to share this truth in a very simple way when he says: "Life's fairy story sees good in evil and light / in the deepest darkness" (*Noon* 12). No doubt, it is night and it is only in night, one can see heaven's light. The poet writes: "How night is night; and through it / To enter the kingdom where Orion turns" (*Noon* 51). It is night that will lead to the morning—the morning of realization, the morning of awakening. The poet continues his journey here in this world and will continue even after his departure from this world. He writes about the journey—journey between life and death, between morning and night. P. Laxminarayana Bhat evaluates Mahapatra's poetry and finds that "All his poetry is a journey into the self in an attempt to understand the mysteries of life (63).

Jayanta Mahapatra respects woman and attempts to present her in all shades. It is only Jayanta Mahapatra who can paint the complete picture of a woman in just four lines containing only nine words. The poem "Woman" reflects a woman's predictable and unpredictable nature.

Even
when she is
Even
when she is not. (*Close the Sky* 44)

A woman searches for her identity, but fails to find it. She feels something missing in her person. Waiting becomes her destiny. She feels lonelier than ever when she finds her man going away after making the physical relationship.

In the darkened room
a woman
cannot find her reflection in the mirror
waiting as usual
at the edge of sleep. (*Rites* 7)

Mahapatra presents the miserable plight of a woman in the character of Chelammal who suffers much because of the male dominated society. Marriage is nothing except a play to trap her. She finds that her life is irrelevant and meaningless.

There is no woman
who is not alone,

no woman who is sure
she has found her way
to her real purpose of life. (*Temple 30*)

She is dominated and exploited, sometimes in the name of poverty and sometimes in the name of the male power. Prostitution is just a disease that results out of hunger of belly as well as of loin. The hunger of the belly forces a fisherman to get his 15-year-old daughter engaged in prostitution. The poem "Hunger" leaves many questions which strike the mind of the reader. The fisherman uses all the tactics in order to trap the protagonist as a customer for his daughter. Here, the poet presents the mental states of both the protagonist and the fisherman thus:

I heard him say: My daughter, she's just turned fifteen...
Feel her. I'll be back soon, your bus leaves at nine.
The sky fell on me, and a father's exhausted wife.
Long and lean, her years were cold as rubber.
She opened her wormy legs wide. I felt the hunger there,
the other one, the fish slithering, turning inside. (*Rites 44*)

Mahapatra voices his feelings when he sees the present state of his country and finds it in the grip of corruption, over-population, unemployment, pollution and terrorism. He is shocked when he sees "the women restless" and history reposing "between the college girl's breasts" (*A Father's Hours 27*). He fails to understand the psychology of his pretty neighbour Mina who "flashes round and round the gilded stage/ hiding jungles in her purse, holding on to her divorce, and a lonely Ph.D." (*A Father's Hours 27*)

Mahapatra weeps over the pathetic condition of his country, and particularly of women who are being raped and exploited. He feels helpless and hopeless when he fails to do anything for them. Everyone sees, feels, but remains inactive. Very realistically he presents the scene and his reaction to it thus:

In the paddy fields beyond,
a daughter of the village
lies mutilated and dead,
...And I don't know
what I am waiting for. (*Land 45*)

Mahapatra is quite conscious of the environment and, so, he talks of its preservation for saving humanity. He finds that the mother earth is being polluted in the name of growth and progress. Man becomes cruel when he disrobes it without taking into consideration of the environmental pollution. The earth also weeps, but the man fails to see its pain.

We disrobed the earth
under everyone's eyes,

every afternoon now
 pain peers from its pores
 folded in
 little weeds. (*Hesitant Light* 91)

Mahapatra is against the rituals which have become a part and parcel of the Indian people, particularly Orissans. He frankly admits before Norman Simms: "I don't think I am a religious person in the way most Indians are. Frankly, I am not. ... I do not believe in ritual, which seems to hold so much for people; the Indian religions are steeped in ritual, which appears meaningless. My concept of religion would be not to hurt others, or *try* not to do so." (306) The poet mentions a 13-year-old servant girl who died of tetanus "even though/ she had begun fasting scrupulously every festival-day/ ... And returned from the temple with the goddess's vermilion." (*Burden* 29) He reveals the hypocrisy and the irreligious attitude of the religious people. Rape in the temple or nearby cannot be imagined but it happens. He mentions the case of a fishergirl who is raped by the priest's son.

In the Hanuman Temple last night
 the priest's pomaded jean-clad son
 raped the squint-eyed fourteen-year fishergirl
 on the cracked stone platform behind the shrine. (*Life Signs* 26)

The poet sees his ageing mother who has faith in the Lord. She wishes to be cremated at Puri which is a swargadwara that will take the soul to heaven:

her last wish to be cremated here
 twisting uncertainly like light
 on the shifting sands. (*Rites* 28)

Language is what counts for Mahapatra. He himself admits: "When language fails, poetry fails too" (*Door* 199). For him, "Poetry is about making language happen. It is we who push our language to do things in all spheres of our lives" (*Door* 199). He flows with the language, which in turn, makes his thought flow. For instance:

All my senses,
 prisoners of my guilt,
 stop from time to time
 to breathe in the night air,
 as though the damp September wind
 held all that was left of truth and goodness. (*Dawns* 184)

"The form is the thing" (*Close the Sky* 9) which becomes a passion for Mahapatra who uses it in poetry as well as in life. He employs lively and striking images. Here is the scene of copulation between a bull and a cow:

A black humped bull rides the cow
two gods copulating on the warm tar,
the morning closed,
the grass throbbing, cruelly ablaze. (*Rites* 30)

He also adopts the technique of asking question after question. This technique creates a link of curiosity in the mind of the reader who also begins to search for the answers:

Does death ever take us to life
to wait for some purpose? (*Hesitant Light* 81)

As he is from the science discipline, he uses the scientific words in a very natural manner. Here is an excerpt which proves his use of scientific words.

All our deaths ring like bells;
become the pitiful constant of time and gravitation,
the energy equation that open doors behind us,
an interstellar space filling the empty glass. (*False Start* 75)

Innovative scientific phrases like "the flaring magnesium of a smile" (*Relationship* 23) "a galvanometer needle between the zero and the hundred of gloom" (*Relationship* 24) add an extra charm to his poetry. He employs figures like simile, metaphor, personification etc. in order to give feeling and idea to the poem. For instance:

Simile:

friendship is like a pool of water
where shadows move about and dance. (*Relationship* 15)

Metaphor:

Truth is a sheep lying with its newborn lamb. (*Bare Face* 48)

Personification:

the morning laughs softly. (*Hesitant Light* 41)

"Jayanta Mahapatra," as Ujjal Dutta writes, is "essentially an inward-looking poet, a poet of consciousness/" (287) Possessing a mythic consciousness, he explores the silence of his self. He uses symbols and adopts techniques of irony and juxtaposition for creating a poetic effect. His poetry is coloured with his identification with Orissan landscapes, his cultural consciousness, originality of his thoughts, and depth of feelings. His heart cries when he sees the present condition of the society. He finds pain everywhere and this is the pain which connects all the human beings. He knows that "pain's blood is human." (*Random Descent* 66) As his heart cries, he feels burden and to unburden this burden, he begins to write. He himself admits: "I sing because I'm afraid of my heart's cry." (*Hesitant Light* 94) Though his poetry is local, it becomes universal as he succeeds in turning local into global. He crosses the boundary of nation and reaches the international realm where all the human beings are like him. It is pain that connects the hearts of all the human beings. He talks of

suffering, pain, frustration and despair. He becomes so engaged with an idea that he begins to go into the depth and while going there he forgets to come out. The reader also dives deep with him and is lost in Mahapatra's tragic consciousness as he associates himself with the poet. Hence, his poetry is universal. Rabindra K. Swain is right when he says: "While the idiom of Mahapatra's poetry is governed by an acute awareness of the cultural and socio-political ethos of his native place, his vision transcends all national boundaries to achieve a universal significance." (7)

What though Jayanta Mahapatra is not alive today, he is alive in the hearts of the poetry lovers who will never forget him and, thus, continue to remember him for his inimitable contribution to the field of Indian Poetry in English.

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